

Impact of Parental Encouragement on Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies among Senior Secondary Students

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Abstract: This study examines the effects of encouragement from parents on the optimistic and pessimistic inclinations of students in senior secondary schools. Using a survey with 384 participants, the association between parental encouragement and emotional inclinations was measured using correlation and regression analyses. There were also findings to suggest a significant positive correlation between encouragement from parents and optimism ($r = 0.579$, $p < 0.01$) and negative with pessimism ($r = 0.646$, $p < 0.01$). Regression analysis suggests that the effect of encouragement from parents explained about 41.8% variance in pessimism ($R^2 = 0.418$, $p < 0.001$) with a very significant association. Reliability tests further validate the strength of constructs while the values of Cronbach's Alpha range between 0.738 and 0.847. Descriptive statistics indicate that optimism scores have a positive magnitude $M = 3.5370$, more than that of the pessimism scores, $M = 2.4813$, which indicates an overall prevalence of positivity. Future studies can also focus on intervention schemes that engage parenting and other variables like peer influence and socio-economic status. This study highlights the value of programs aimed at guidance from parents in adolescents' psychological development, such as mainstreaming the role of parents in learning and development environments.

Keywords: Parental encouragement, Optimism, Pessimism, Emotional well-being, Senior secondary students

1. Introduction

Nowadays, life has gotten more intricate owing to advancements in science and technology. Everyone is striving to promote advancements in education, driven by the pressures of global economic competition, ongoing modernization, and an increased focus on technology. A child's life is greatly influenced by their parents. Since parents are the ones who know their children the best, they are the best instructors by nature. All parents want their children to succeed in life, thus the role that parents play in their children's success is crucial. The parents' legitimate job is to support, encourage, and provide their children access to activities that help them master important developmental tasks (Akhter & Pandey, 2018). The most important aspect influencing the lives of the current generation is parental encouragement. This is due to the fact that children acquire social standards first in the home and subsequently at school. The conduct of parents has a significant impact on a person's development both now and in the future. A child's development is halted when they are not given proper family care. Children's feelings and emotions should be taken care of by parents. Throughout life, it is important to show gratitude and encourage others. A kid who is left in a state of perplexity since his parents never encourage him to keep his feelings to himself (Lata & Sharma, 2014).

Parents always want the best for their children and hope that they will have better lives than they did. Parents provide their children as many resources as they can, but sometimes this may also have a detrimental effect on their education. When parents inspire or provide their children additional support for their active participation in school, this is known as parental encouragement. The development of children's lives is significantly influenced by parental encouragement (Lawrence & Barathi, 2016). Parental encouragement refers to the care that parents provide their kids, which may help them develop their potential. It may take the shape of direction, care, worry, or approval, and it may serve as motivation for the kids to choose a certain life choice. Children's careers may be made or broken by their parents' support, care, and direction, particularly in the field of education. Parents' prompt assistance and direction may make a huge difference. Parental encouragement may really assist the kid in overcoming a variety of obstacles in life, particularly in the academic realm. Parental encouragement includes approving or disapproving educational activities, easing any challenges pupils may be experiencing, and offering guidance on both positive and negative aspects of the process (Narad & Abdullah, 2016).

In order for children to succeed academically and in life, parental encouragement in upper secondary education is crucial. According to studies, parental involvement and encouragement in education are linked to (i) higher test scores and grades, (ii) improved attendance, (iii) higher rates of homework completion, (iv) an increase in positive attitudes and behaviors at home and at school, (v) higher graduation rates, (vi) higher college attendance rates, (vii) higher overall student achievement, (viii) a better attitude toward school and specific subject areas, (ix) more time spent on homework and studying, and (x) better self-concept, etc. (Lawrence & Barathi, 2016).

Adolescence is marked by a number of noteworthy changes in the social, emotional, cognitive, and physical realms. Adolescents must learn the appropriate coping mechanisms when they face a variety of developmental obstacles. Identity consolidation is a significant difficulty for teenagers (Jackson & Goossens, 2006). The development of autonomy toward their parents goes hand in hand with this difficulty. In the meanwhile, teenagers may feel more negative emotions and be more emotionally reactive at this time. The degree to which teenagers manage and overcome these developmental obstacles has a profound and enduring effect on their mental health (Kennes et al., 2021). One element that helps to support academic success and achievement motivation is optimism.

Optimism serves as a bridge between an individual's evaluation and external occurrences. A person may learn to attribute optimism via the impact of their social environment, even if hereditary factors also play a role. The conviction that one will experience favourable outcomes is known as optimism. Optimism, often known as the anticipation of favourable outcomes, seems to have a connection to both mental and physical health. High optimism has been linked to low levels of anxiety and cognitive distortion, as well as high levels of psychological resilience and self-esteem. People who are optimistic take a positive outlook on life, are able to manage stress, believe that they will encounter favourable circumstances in the future, and attribute favourable internal factors to favourable experiences. Research has shown that when faced with stressful and unpleasant circumstances, those with a dominant optimistic outlook report greater subjective well-being than those who are pessimistic (Tras et al., 2021).

Pessimism and optimism are associated with various motivational processes, as per the theoretical foundations of dispositional optimism. Theories of motivation based on expectancy value have a longstanding history and are linked to the concepts of optimism and pessimism. Expectancy-value theories assert that behaviour is the outcome of striving for goals. The value of a goal escalates in accordance with its significance to the individual. Expectancy, defined as the conviction that the goal may be achieved, is the second fundamental concept of this motivational framework. Optimism or pessimism is characterised by an individual's confidence or scepticism in their potential for success. While the contrast between optimism and pessimism looks easy, it also seems to be extremely consequential (Scheier & Carver, 2018). Poor communication between students and instructors, depressive symptoms, poor learning outcomes, and a tendency for kids to commit school infractions, which affect low self-esteem, are all indicators of low optimism in students. A person who is optimistic has a favorable outlook on the future, which is important for their psychological health (Li et al., 2023). Seligman says that optimism is a dynamic aspect of positive psychology that is intimately associated with optimistic future-focused thoughts (Özpehriz, 2020). In addition to being more content with their children's academic success, optimistic parents are also more effective parents (Castro-Schilo et al., 2013). When it comes to the relationship between parental style and children's optimism, children who have communicative, authoritarian parents are more optimistic than those who have an authoritarian approach. A higher degree of optimism has been linked to moderate parental control over children, whereas depressed symptoms have often been seen in children who have been given little autonomy. At the same time, the findings demonstrated that the child's optimism is impacted by the mother's depressed symptoms and that the mother's pessimism is connected with the child's pessimism (Hasan & Power, 2002). Parental encouragement and adolescents' optimistic or pessimistic dispositions are topics of increasing interest, especially regarding the effects of these on the academic and psychological development of students. Although studies have indicated a broader role for parental encouragement in supporting academic achievement, there have been fewer efforts to examine in more detail the ways in which it shapes optimism and pessimism among senior secondary students. This gap is important at this stage of development, for it is at this age that adolescents make seminal decisions regarding education and career choice, and the outlook on life at this juncture will determine much of what they decide. This study looks at the direct and indirect impact of parental encouragement on the psychological tendencies of adolescents through optimism and pessimism as the salient variables to explore. It will analyze how kinds of parental support emotional, academic, and motivational impact the way students perceive threats or opportunities when facing challenges.

This study contributes to both the theoretical and practical domains by integrating insights from positive psychology and developmental psychology. It provides action-oriented recommendations to parents, educators, and policymakers about how to create an environment that can foster optimism while reducing pessimism among adolescents, thus opening doors to developing interventions targeted at the emotional needs of students for support beyond academic goals toward holistic development.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Parental Encouragement and Its Role in Adolescent Development

An increasing number of researchers are looking at the underlying factors that link teenagers' participation in general computer activities with parental encouragement. Teenagers' trust in technology is one such factor. It is often known that teenagers are more inclined to engage in and learn from related activities if they have more confidence in their technical prowess (Shank & Cotten, 2014). However, when compared to their male peers, this connection may not apply to African American female teenagers. Despite having the capacity to participate in and excel in science and mathematics, female teenagers of all races are often less confident in their technical prowess than their male counterparts. According to (Stoet & Geary, 2018), female teenagers often do better in other courses than math, science, or technology. As a result, they may lack faith in technology, which discourages them from using it further. As a result, African American female teenagers may exhibit lower levels of technical confidence than other genders.

Teenagers spend a significant amount of time with their families at home when they are not in school. Teenagers' interests and confidence in technology may be sparked by their relationships with their parents. According to studies on related subjects like science and math, parents who encourage their children more report higher levels of interest in these subjects among White and African American sixth-graders as well as Latinx, African American, Asian American, and multiracial high school students. Adolescents' use of technology may also be favorably correlated with parental encouragement. Teenagers' faith in technology may be negatively impacted by parents' possible discriminatory treatment of male and female adolescents (e.g., more likely to encourage male adolescents) (Tenenbaum & Leaper, 2003). In order to contextualize the possible gender disparity in African American teenagers' technology involvement and parenting experiences, it is crucial to take into account the responsibilities of both parents and adolescents.

2.2 Understanding Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies in Adolescents

Optimism, as defined by (Carver & Scheier, 2014), is a disposition that acts as a buffer between the subject's external environment and how they perceive it. An optimistic perspective enables the person to react constructively to challenging, stressful, and even painful situations, enabling them to overcome these obstacles with hard work and perseverance. Similarly, a person's resilience and attention in evaluating their unique situation determine whether they will be optimistic or pessimistic. Therefore, depending on perception, circumstances and their consequence may be seen from both an optimistic and pessimistic angle.

The research now in publication emphasizes the connection between optimism and a number of psychological traits. In addition to being less likely to experience intrapersonal vulnerability, and personal sadness, optimistic people are also more likely to exhibit adaptive behaviour (Carver & Scheier, 2014), have high hopes for future accomplishments (Segerstrom, 2006), and be personally efficient (Martínez-Correa et al., 2006). They contend that optimistic people handle challenges better and get sick less frequently than pessimistic people, and they are less likely to experience stress, fatigue, and cynicism.

Adolescent optimism has received very little attention. More positive students' social and personal connections may result in improved academic achievement. According to research,

optimism is associated with greater levels of assertiveness, self-efficacy, self-esteem, and self-concept (Usán Supervía et al., 2020).

Therefore, optimism is important in a person's life, particularly throughout childhood and adolescence, when adult personality is formed as a permanent dispositional trait. In adolescence, students' cognitive powers or skills about their expectations and social comparison with their peers are revealed, but in infancy, optimism develops based on the experience of good or unsatisfactory events, according to those closest to the kid. As a result, it's critical to teach youngsters optimism in order to promote proper moral and personal growth (Rand, 2018).

2.3 Interrelationship Between Parental Encouragement and Emotional Tendencies

The implication of parental encouragement in shaping the emotional tendency of students has long been overtaken by academic outcomes. But, quite across all disciplines, a broad range of non-cognitive skills and competencies in emotional aspects have been found to play significant parts in achievements and overall welfare of a person, which goes beyond the attaining of educational milestones to affect long-term development, both personally and professionally (Kennedy & Sundberg, 2020); (Patrinos, 2021). The present study focuses on one critical aspect of this interrelationship, the influence of parental encouragement on children's emotional development (Chernyshenko et al., 2018). Emotional tendencies, which are largely influenced by parental support, have been linked to higher self-esteem, better stress management, and improved social interactions, all of which contribute to academic success (Wang & Cheung, 2023), emotional resilience (Guerra et al., 2014), and overall well-being and life satisfaction (Salmela-Aro & Upadyaya, 2020). When children are positively encouraged by parents, they become more likely to develop positive emotional tendencies, including optimism, empathy, and control of emotions that help them get through challenges inside and outside of school. Furthermore, parental involvement in the facilitation of emotional well-being is likely to build a child's decision-making, social adaptability, and ability to resolve conflict, thus establishing a basis for a well-rounded and emotionally intelligent individual. Recognizing the interrelated role of parental support and emotional tendencies, educators and parents can contribute to a nurturing environment that promotes holistic development and emotional well-being.

2.4 Research gap

Although several research has been done on how parents affect student academic achievement and self-efficacy, less empirical data supports the link between parental encouragement and optimistic and pessimistic dispositions. Furthermore, earlier studies have not given enough attention to gender inequalities in parental encouragement and its emotional effect as well as socio-cultural variations. Therefore, this study attempts to close this gap by investigating whether greater parental support is noticeably linked to lower pessimism and more optimism among kids. Unlike most cross-sectional research, the current one is a call for a comprehensive strategy that considers long-term consequences, thus allowing one to explore the function of parental encouragement in the growth of kids' emotional resilience.

2.5 Research Questions

- How does parental encouragement influence pessimistic tendencies among senior secondary students?
- What is the relationship between parental encouragement and optimistic tendencies among students?

- Do senior secondary students with high parental encouragement exhibit significantly higher levels of optimism?

2.6 Research Objectives

- To examine the influence of parental encouragement on the pessimistic tendencies of senior secondary school students.
- To analyze the relationship between parental encouragement and optimistic tendencies among students.
- To determine whether senior secondary students with high parental encouragement exhibit significantly higher levels of optimism.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Research Design

The current research uses a cross-sectional design that assesses the role of parental support in students' emotional propensities toward Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies among senior secondary students. In this context, a cross-sectional design will be advantageous since it will efficiently gather data at a single point in time, demonstrating any correlation between parental encouragement and optimism and pessimism outcomes. This is easier to use the data gathered from participants about the influence of the involvement of their parents on students' emotional conditions. The cross-sectional approach facilitates a comprehensive perspective through organized information collecting, hypothesis testing, and statistical analysis, offering an overview of the current situation.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

The study's conceptual framework explores the interrelations of parental encouragement, emotional tendencies (optimism and pessimism), and academic performance among senior secondary students (Figure 1). This hypothesizes that parental encouragement is the most important factor that shapes the students' emotional state; thus, their optimism levels increase and their pessimistic tendencies are reduced. Focusing on parental involvement in academic, emotional, and social aspects, the study seeks to provide a complete understanding of how parental encouragement influences emotional development in educational contexts. This concept is essential for understanding the impact of parental encouragement on creating a healthy emotional environment, which may greatly influence children's well-being and academic performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3.3 Hypotheses

- **H0:** Parental encouragement does not significantly reduce pessimistic tendencies among senior secondary students.
H1: Parental encouragement significantly reduces pessimistic tendencies among senior secondary students.
- **H0:** There is no significant correlation between parental encouragement and optimistic tendencies among students.
H2: There is a significant correlation between parental encouragement and optimistic tendencies among students.
- **H0:** Senior secondary students with high parental encouragement do not exhibit significantly higher levels of optimism.
H3: Senior secondary students with high parental encouragement will exhibit higher levels of optimism.

3.4 Data Collection Tools and Techniques

The technique of stratified random sampling was used to choose participants from the senior secondary schools. This helps ensure that each subgroup within the population is adequately represented in the sample, and therefore, study findings are representative. A total of 384 students participated in the study, thus creating a good data set for analysis. Data collected was through the use of a structured questionnaire targeting parental encouragement and Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies. The survey specifically targeted adolescents aged 13 to 18 years and included questions related to perceived Parental Encouragement, optimism, and pessimism. This questionnaire aimed to capture, with accuracy, the depth of involvement by parents on the various academic, emotional, and social dimensions as well as scales used in measuring students' optimistic and pessimistic tendencies. The reliability of the collecting tools was confirmed by administering them during a testing procedure. To analyse the data, descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and correlation tests were employed using SPSS software. These statistical techniques thus made it possible to critically evaluate the study's hypotheses and thereby better understand the relationships existing between parental encouragement and students' Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies.

3.5 Measures

➤ Parental Encouragement

Parental encouragement is the process by which parents support, motivate, and guide their children's behaviour, especially toward academic achievement. It can also include providing emotional support and helping children develop good habits and ideas, parental encouragement was measured in a standardized 5-item questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale. This questionnaire has a spectrum that ranges between "strongly disagree" having a score of 1 while "strongly agree" corresponds to a score of 5. The measure encompasses several facets of parental involvement such as giving emotional support and motivational encouragement with involvement in academic or extracurricular activities.

➤ Optimistic Tendencies

Optimistic attitudes, which define optimism and being optimistic, contribute to a more significant improvement in physical and mental health, day-to-day activities, and quality of life in general. It brightens up moods, helps increase resilience to illness, hastens recovery time from illness, improves stress coping, and helps better bear traumatic experiences and stress.

The questionnaire applied a validated scale of 5 items rated on a five-point Likert scale whereby "1" represented "strongly disagree" and 5 "strongly agree". The dimensions the scale had applied were future expectations, resilience when presented with challenges and confidence in realizing personal goals.

➤ **Pessimistic Tendencies**

This pessimistic mindset believes bad things are commonplace and holds little hope for the future. Individuals need to label negative thoughts, focus on different things, slow down, admit difficult emotions, and prepare for difficult situations but still hope for the best. It was measured by a 5-item scale which, like the one above, is Likert-scaled on a five-point range where 1 represents "strongly disagree" and 5 indicates "strongly agree." The items measure the scale dimensions including doubting one's success, being prone to expectation of failure, and feelings of powerlessness.

4. Result

This study determined whether parental encouragement affects optimism and pessimistic emotions in the case of senior secondary school students. The data for cross-sectional study samples were collected in a manner that provides representation about the degree of parental encouragement and Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies rates as well as relationships among variables. Hypothesized correlations and relationships were examined by applying suitable correlation and regression tests. The findings are such that it reveals encouragement from parents plays an important role in shaping the students' Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies. Higher levels of parental encouragement showed a positive relationship with higher optimism and lower pessimism. Additionally, the data demonstrate that parental participation was positively correlated with optimism, and reduced pessimistic among secondary school students. These results highlight how important parental encouragement is for kids' emotional health and resilience, which is why it's important in educational and developmental settings.

Table 1: Internal Consistency and Convergent Validity

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
Parental Encouragement	0.844	0.795	0.609
Optimism	0.738	0.835	0.697
Pessimism	0.847	0.811	0.640

Table 1 depicts the reliability and convergent validity of the variables Parental Encouragement, Optimism, and Pessimism. The Cronbach's Alpha for the constructs was within an acceptable to high internal consistency ranging from 0.738 to 0.847. The figures above demonstrate how items are uniformly measuring what the intended construct would have aimed at measuring in a particular variable.

The Reliability scores, which fall between 0.795 and 0.835, further support the constructs' dependability since values over 0.7 indicate strong internal consistency. AVE scores range from 0.609 to 0.697, showing good convergent validity and above the recommended threshold of 0.5. Particularly, Parental Encouragement shows an AVE of 0.609, while Optimism gives

an AVE of 0.697, and Pessimism holds an AVE of 0.640, all that to confirm that the constructs are indeed able to explain the variance in their respective items quite well.

In summary, the findings based on Cronbach's Alpha, CR, and AVE establish high reliability and convergent validity of these psychological variables. These findings provide a strong foundation for future studies and help to clarify how parental encouragement, optimism, and pessimism interact in a particular situation.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Parental Encouragement	3.7031	.71404
Optimism	3.5370	.86117
Pessimism	2.4813	1.08349

Table 2 provides a summary of the descriptive statistics for three variables: Parental Encouragement, Optimism, and Pessimism. Mean values for each of the variables reflect the central tendency to provide insights into the perception of the participants. On Parental Encouragement, the mean score was at 3.7031, reflecting a moderate level of encouragement perceived among participants. A standard deviation of 0.71404 indicates a little variability in the responses; it thus depicts that the subjects hold a consistent attitude toward Parental Encouragement. The optimism has a mean of 3.5370, suggesting a positive direction generally; however, the scores show variation as a standard deviation of 0.86117 suggesting that though most of the participants maintain an optimistic attitude, a few of them have more optimism. Conversely, the score of Pessimism is quite low, 2.4813, showing that respondents generally tend less to have negative thinking.

The standard deviation of 1.08349 is larger, which means that responses vary more in their levels of pessimism. This indicates that while some participants experience minimal pessimism, others experience higher degrees of pessimistic outlooks. The descriptive statistics, then, show moderately high levels of parental encouragement with optimism and diversified levels of pessimism. These results provide fundamental insight into the occurrence of emotional features among the individuals, which allows for a more detailed investigation of their interrelationships.

Table 3: Discriminant validity

	Parental Encouragement	Optimism	Pessimism
Parental Encouragement	0.780		
Optimism	-0.003	0.834	
Pessimism	0.646	0.012	0.8

Table 3 illustrates the summary results of the correlation coefficients for Parental Encouragement, Optimism, and Pessimism. These values represent the magnitude and direction for each relationship of the variables under study. Thus, Parental Encouragement itself yields a very high and positive association ($r = 0.780$), which indicates internal

consistency. In addition, Optimism also has a highly significant positive correlation ($r = 0.834$), which indicates that with an increasing amount of parental encouragement, optimism level increases. However, the correlation between Parental Encouragement and Pessimism is very weakly observed at $r = 0.646$, which means that, although both are related, the relationship is not as strong as that for optimism. Optimism and Pessimism have a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.012$, which indicates almost no direct relationship between the variables. Overall, it can be seen that the table does reflect interrelation among parental encouragement, optimism, and pessimism with very clear-cut positive as well as weak associations and the variable of optimism was the strongest across all.

H1: Parental encouragement significantly reduces pessimistic tendencies among senior secondary students.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.646 ^a	.418	.416	.65811

a. Predictors: (Constant), Parental encouragement

The model summary for Table 4 explains the relationship that exists between the encouragement of parents and pessimism. The Pearson correlation coefficient is set at 0.646 and indicates a moderate positive relation between parental encouragement and levels of pessimism, meaning that high levels of encouragement from parents coincide with moderate or rising levels of pessimism.

The R^2 value, or the coefficient of determination, is 0.418, meaning that approximately 41.8% of the variability in pessimism can be explained by parental encouragement. The remaining 58.2% of the variability is due to other factors not included in the model.

The adjusted R^2 value is at 0.416, where the adjustment happens to account for the number of predictors in the model. Its value is such that it denotes a slightly lowered proportion of explained variability by parental encouragement alone. However, it still reflects a contribution toward understanding the impacts of parental encouragement on pessimism. Overall, this model gives a reasonably good fit towards the data-capturing portion of the variability in pessimism.

Table 5: ANOVA

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	118.588	1	118.588	273.808	.000 ^b
	Residual	165.447	382	.433		
	Total	284.035	383			

a. Dependent Variable: Pessimism
b. Predictors: (Constant), Parental encouragement

The ANOVA test (Table 5) tests the statistical significance of the overall regression model using the data given. With an F-statistic value of 273.808 and a significance value of 0.000, it is very evident that it is below the threshold of 0.05.

Table 6: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.651	.178	3.667	.000
	Parental_encouragement1	.779	.047	.646	16.547

a. Dependent Variable: Pessimism

The coefficient (Table 6), when not standardized for the relationship between parental encouragement on pessimism is 0.779. For everyone's increase in parental encouragement, pessimism decreased by 0.779 units. Its t-value is 16.547. The P-value is 0.000. The t-value lies far beyond a value of 2, and a P-value exists way beyond the value of 0.05, hence demonstrating a good statistical association between encouragement provided by the parent and lesser occurrence of pessimism. Thus, we might conclude that reduced levels of pessimism are correlated with increased parental encouragement, a confirmation of how supportive parental involvement has a big impact on decreased depressing outlooks.

H2: There is a significant correlation between parental encouragement and optimistic tendencies among students.

Table 7: Correlations

	Parental encouragement	Optimistic
Parental encouragement	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.579**
	N	384
Optimistic	Pearson Correlation	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	384

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 7 shows the association between parental encouragement and optimism. The Pearson correlation coefficient that exists between parental encouragement and optimism is 0.579 and has a P-value of 0.000 (2-tailed). This was a strong positive relationship, indicating that higher parental encouragement levels would be significantly related to greater levels of optimism for individuals. The correlation is highly significant at 0.01. Parental Encouragement would be very much important for generating an optimistic perspective. The conclusion is that these findings may depict the fact that parental encouragement actually plays a fundamental role in enhancing optimistic attitudes leading to better psychological wellbeing and resilience.

H3: Senior secondary students with high parental encouragement will exhibit higher levels of optimism.

Table 8: Group Statistics

	Parental Encouragement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Optimistic	Low parental encouragement	202	3.7224	.85369	.06007
	High parental encouragement	182	3.8857	.72121	.05346

Group Statistics (Table 8) Comparison Between Parental Encouragement and Optimism of the Individual The table below compares parental encouragement and its relationship with optimism levels as perceived by individuals: Analyzing the results, where low parental encouragement was attributed to 202, their optimism mean score stood at 3.7224, with a standard deviation of 0.85369 and a standard error of 0.06007. In contrast, individuals who have high parental encouragement (N = 182) recorded a greater mean score with optimism of 3.8857, whose standard deviation was 0.72121 and the standard error 0.05346. This suggests that people who have higher parental encouragement tend to be more optimistic, showing a very high positive impact of Parental Encouragement to create a more optimistic mindset.

Table 9: Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Optimistic	Equal variances assumed	6.068	.014	-2.013	382	.045	-.16327	.08112
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.030	380.456	.043	-.16327	.08041

This independent samples t-test (Table 9) assesses whether there is a difference in levels of optimism between the two groups. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances returned an F-value of 6.068 with a p-value of 0.014, so the variances between the groups are not equal. For the equal variances t-test, the t-value is -2.013, and the df = 382. The p-value is 0.045. The mean difference is -0.16327 with a standard error difference of 0.08112. The 95% Confidence Interval for the difference ranges from -0.32276 to -0.00378. If the variances are not assumed, then the t-test is significant with a t-value of -2.030, df = 380.456, and a p-value of 0.043. The uniform mean difference was found as -0.16327 with a standard error difference of 0.08041. Thus, the 95% Confidence Interval ranges from -0.32138 to -0.00517. This indicates a statistically significant difference in optimism levels between the groups, implying that group membership substantially influences optimism.

5. Discussion

The significant impact of parental encouragement towards the academic performances of secondary school students in West Bengal. Application of the Descriptive Survey Method and stratified random sampling created a comprehensive coverage, which thus showed a robust positive relationship existing between parental encouragement and the respective academic performance levels of the respondents (Bhatia & Mishra, 2024). This leads to consistency with the other research that establishes the irreplaceable position of parents as saviours to secure the

future educational success of their children. The use of Karl Pearson's product-moment correlation again enhances the value of parent involvement. Even though there are limitations to the research conducted, it makes an essential call for fostering parental involvement with the help of PTA and orientation. The said activity may further enhance their awareness of children, thus promoting education and leading towards the overall growth of a child.

This crucial role optimism, pessimism, and locus of control play in both adolescent and educator academic success and well-being. It involves how a positive outlook, an internal locus of control, and positive thoughts can be correlated with proactive problem-solving and goal setting for greater achievement in academe and emotional well-being (Ali, 2024). Negative attitudes and an external locus of control are associated with lower motivation and decreased performance. Educators are instrumental in instilling these qualities through positive interactions and encouraging personal responsibility and self-efficacy. Moreover, educational policies that include social-emotional learning and supportive environments have to be provided to ensure that the child develops well-roundedly. By equipping students with psychological tools to cope with setbacks and thrive academically and emotionally, schools empower learners to succeed in both their personal and educational journeys.

The purpose of this research is to establish the effects of parental encouragement on the Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies of senior secondary school students, including optimism and pessimism. Parental encouragement appears to be an important determinant of students' welfare. Students receiving higher levels of encouragement tended to have more optimistic and lower levels of pessimistic Tendencies. The descriptive statistics reported that students had perceived moderate to high levels of support from their parents and that this in turn influenced the students' outlooks. This is supported further by the regression analysis, as it shows very strong positive correlations between parental encouragement and both optimism and a reduction in pessimism. Moreover, variation in the emotional tendencies of students shows that though Parental Encouragement increases the positive emotions, it also decreases the negative ones. These findings show the importance of parent involvement as a means toward the establishment of a well-balanced emotional level, where proper and consistent efforts by parents pushing in the direction of resilience and optimism can impact students' growth significantly in regard to emotions. Therefore, these findings show the importance of such parental encouragement among critical determinants influencing the growth of emotions for students.

Both discussions emphasize the role of parental involvement in student's emotional and academic development, with differing emphases. Other discussions focus on the direct implications of encouraging Parental Encouragement in academic performances and developing optimism through goal setting and resilience. Our discussion, however, centers on how the support of parents shifts the Optimistic and Pessimistic Tendencies of optimism versus pessimism; in so doing, there is a strong implication that encouraging Parental Encouragement has a correlation with emotional well-being. Both discuss the function of teachers and social circumstances in promoting positive psychological attributes, but our research emphasizes the subtlety of parents' engagement in the balance of emotions. Furthermore, whereas other conversations focus on social-emotional learning and extra-familial resource networks, the conversation for us is about how parental encouragement individually impacts the emotional development of students, representing an alternative, more student-specific understanding.

This collective view therefore underlines the complex relationship of Parental Encouragement both to achievement at school and to psychological well-being.

6. Limitations

Although this study has limitations, it provides insightful information about the relationship between senior secondary students' optimism, pessimism, and parental encouragement. Firstly, the cross-sectional design makes it impossible to prove causation and self-reported data could be biased.

Other functions of parents, such as providing emotional support or punishment, were not examined. This study also does not take into consideration some key factors such as peer relationships, mental health, and socioeconomic issues. T

Future studies can be conducted using more comprehensive factors like peer and teacher support using qualitative approaches, varied samples, and longitudinal designs in order to gain a detailed and more generalizable emotional development.

7. Conclusion

This study deals with the relationship of parental encouragement, optimism, and pessimism among senior secondary students. The results indicate that encouragement from parents has a great influence on students' emotional outlooks. More specifically, parental encouragement is closely positively related to optimism ($r = 0.579$, $p < 0.01$) and moderately positively related to pessimism ($r = 0.646$, $p < 0.01$). These results indicate that higher levels of parental encouragement are associated with greater optimism and slightly reduced pessimism among students.

From descriptive statistics, a moderately high score in parental encouragement is seen; that is to say, its mean was 3.7031. The corresponding standard deviation has been 0.71404, which would suggest slight variations in responses. Optimism received a mean score of 3.5370 while its standard deviation had been 0.86117. This points out a mostly optimistic attitude, yet with certain variations. Conversely, pessimism is characterized by a lower mean score of 2.4813 and its standard deviation, which is significantly higher at 1.08349, as well.

Further regression analysis to the above findings showed that parental encouragement reduced pessimistic tendencies significantly by $\beta = -0.779$, $p < 0.05$; however, optimistic tendencies were positively influenced ($\beta = 0.579$, $p < 0.01$). Findings in the end, therefore, highlighted how students' emotional well-being and resilience can be influenced considerably by support from parents.

This study has practical ramifications for a range of stakeholders, such as parents, educators, and legislators. Students' academic performance and emotional health can both be enhanced by promoting increased parental involvement. Programs for parental engagement can be incorporated into school curricula to help parents understand how their support can help their kids become resilient and optimistic. Counsellors and mental health specialists can also modify programs to highlight how family dynamics affect emotional development. By encouraging these behaviours, we can establish a more harmonious and encouraging atmosphere that fosters kids' emotional development and academic achievement at the same time.

This study further establishes the need of Parental Encouragement towards a more balanced mood to encourage an optimistic mindset and minimize tendencies towards pessimism. This

research increases understanding of the role of Parental Encouragement in students' psychological and mental development, as it seems specific interventions directed at positive outcomes might be established for this aspect

References

1. Akhter, A., & Pandey, S. (2018). A study of parental encouragement on the academic achievement of secondary level students in J & K. *International Journal of Advanced Educational Research*, 3, 500–503.
2. Ali, R. (2024). Study Involvement and Academic Achievement of Secondary Students in West Bengal. *Research Review International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 9, 110-118. <https://doi.org/10.31305/rrijm.2024.v09.n06.015>
3. Bhatia, A. K., & Mishra, H. (2024). An Examination of Optimism/Pessimism and Locus of Control in Adolescents and Educators: Implications for Academic Achievement and Well-Being. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, 6, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i04.24599>
4. Carver, C. S., & Scheier, M. F. (2014). Dispositional optimism. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 18, 293–299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2014.02.003>
5. Castro-Schilo, L., Taylor, Z. E., Ferrer, E., Robins, R. W., Conger, R. D., & Widaman, K. F. (2013). Parents' optimism, positive parenting, and child peer competence in Mexican-origin families. *Parenting*, 13, 95–112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15295192.2012.709151>
6. Chernyshenko, O. S., Kankaraš, M., & Drasgow, F. (2018). Social and emotional skills for student success and well-being: Conceptual framework for the OECD study on social and emotional skills. *OECD Education Working Papers*, OECD Publishing, Paris. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/db1d8e59-en>
7. Guerra, N., Modecki, K., & Cunningham, W. (2014). Developing social-emotional skills for the labor market: The PRACTICE model. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, 7123.
8. Hasan, N., & Power, T. G. (2002). Optimism and pessimism in children: A study of parenting correlates. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 26, 185–191. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/01650250114300003>
9. Jackson, S., & Goossens, L. (2006). *Handbook of adolescent development*. Psychology Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203969861>
10. Kennedy, T. J., & Sundberg, C. W. (2020). 21st century skills. In: Akpan, B., Kennedy, T. J. (eds) *Science Education in Theory and Practice: An Introductory Guide to Learning Theory*, Springer Texts in Education. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-43620-9_32
11. Kennes, A., Peeters, S., Janssens, M., Reijnders, J., Simons, M., Lataster, J., & Jacobs, N. (2021). Optimism and mental health in adolescence: A prospective validation study of the Dutch Life-Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-RA) for adolescents. *Psychologica Belgica*, 61, 104. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5334/pb.799>
12. Lata, S., & Sharma, S. K. (2014). Comparative Study of Optimistic And Pessimistic Attitude of Adolescents in Relation to Their Locality and Parental Encouragement. *International Journal of Behavioral Social and Movement Sciences*, 3, 83–92.
13. Lawrence, A. S., & Barathi, C. (2016). Parental Encouragement in Relation to Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Students. *Online Submission*, 2, 1234–1239.
14. Li, Y., Bressington, D., Wang, S., Leung, S. F., & Mak, Y. W. (2023). Relationship between parental psychological control and optimism among Hong Kong adolescents: The mediating role of self-mastery. *Current Psychology*, 42, 10115–10122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02312-3>

15. Martínez-Correa, A., Reyes del Paso, G. A., García-León, A., & González-Jareño, M. I. (2006). Relationship between dispositional optimism/pessimism and stress coping strategies. *Psicothema*, 18, 66–72.
16. Narad, A., & Abdullah, B. (2016). Academic performance of senior secondary school students: Influence of parental encouragement and school environment. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 8, 12–19. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha.v8n2.02>
17. Özpehriz, H. S. (2020). Positive prevention theory: The investigation of parenting styles as a predictor of optimism. *Research on Education and Psychology*, 4, 114–132.
18. Patrinos, H. A. (2021). The Learning Challenge in the Twenty-first Century. In *Media, Technology and Education in a Post-Truth Society: From Fake News, Datafication and Mass Surveillance to the Death of Trust*. Emerald Publishing Limited, 39–53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80043-906-120211004>
19. Rand, K. L. (2018). Hope, self-efficacy, and optimism: Conceptual and empirical differences. In Gallagher, M. W., & Lopez, S. J. (eds) *The Oxford Handbook of Hope*, Oxford University Press, 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199399314.013.4>
20. Salmela-Aro, K., & Upadyaya, K. (2020). School engagement and school burnout profiles during high school—The role of socio-emotional skills. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 17, 943–964. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405629.2020.1785860>
21. Scheier, M. F., & Carver, C. S. (2018). Dispositional optimism and physical health: A long look back, a quick look forward. *American Psychologist*, 73, 1082. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000384>
22. Segerstrom, S. C. (2006). How does optimism suppress immunity? Evaluation of three affective pathways. *Health Psychology*, 25, 653.
23. Shank, D. B., & Cotten, S. R. (2014). Does technology empower urban youth? The relationship of technology use to self-efficacy. *Computers & Education*, 70, 184–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.08.018>
24. Stoet, G., & Geary, D. C. (2018). The gender-equality paradox in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics education. *Psychological Science*, 29, 581–593. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797617741719>
25. Tenenbaum, H. R., & Leaper, C. (2003). Parent-child conversations about science: The socialization of gender inequities? *Developmental Psychology*, 39, 34–47. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.39.1.34>
26. Tras, Z., SUNBUL, M. G., & Baltaci, U. B. (2021). Investigation of the relationships between optimism, perceived social support, and hope. *i.e.: Inquiry in Education*, 13, 11.
27. Usán Supervía, P., Salavera Bordás, C., & Murillo Lorente, V. (2020). Exploring the psychological effects of optimism on life satisfaction in students: The mediating role of goal orientations. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17, 7887. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17217887>
28. Wang, I. Y., & Cheung, R. Y. M. (2023). Parents' gender role attitudes and child adjustment: The mediating role of parental involvement. *Sex Roles*, 89, 425–441. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-023-01386-6>